

International Journal of

Indagare

Available online at www.indgr.org

Effect of Cyber Aggression on Cyber Victimization among High School Children: Parental Rejection as a Predictor

Authors:

Jakia Rahman, Muhammad Kamal Uddin, Sardar Mohammad Abu Bakar Siddique, Protyasha Bhattacharyya

DOI:

Citation: Rahman, J., Uddin, M. K., Siddique, S. M. A. B., & Bhattacharyya, P. (2020). Effect of Cyber Aggression on Cyber Victimization among High School Children: Parental Rejection as a Predictor. *International Journal of the Asia Pacific School Psychology*, 1(2), 185-191.

Abstract

This study examined how parental rejection affects cyber victimization both directly and indirectly through cyber aggression among high school children in Bangladesh. A convenience sample of 303 high school students (53.5% boys and 46.5% girls) aged 12 to 19 was selected from six schools in Dhaka city. Participants completed a series of adapted self-report questionnaires evaluating demographics, cyber aggression, cyber victimization, and maternal/paternal acceptance-rejection. Correlation analysis indicated that all primary variables were significantly and positively associated with one another. Specifically, higher levels of perceived parental rejection were linked to increased incidents of cyber aggression and victimization. Mediation regression analyses demonstrated that while neither paternal nor maternal rejection had a significant direct effect on cyber victimization, maternal rejection exerted a significant indirect effect mediated through cyber aggression. These findings highlight family dynamics as important factors in addressing adolescent cyberbullying risks.

Effect of Cyber Aggression on Cyber Victimization among High School Children: Parental Rejection as a Predictor

Jakia Rahman, Muhammad Kamal Uddin, Sardar Mohammad
Abu Bakar Siddique, and Protyasha Bhattacharyya
University of Dhaka, Dhaka 1000, Bangladesh.

The present paper studies about how Cybercrime affects the young generation. However, the risk factor of being victimized in cyberspace is unknown. The present study tested predictions that (a) parental rejection might be the risk factor of cyber victimization, and (b) parental rejection can affect cyber victimization partially through cyber aggression among high school children. The sample consisted of 303 high school children (53% boys & 47% girls). Participants' mean age was 14.89 years (SD = 1.11), with a range of 12 through 19 years. They were selected from six different schools of the Dhaka city by using convenience sampling technique. The instruments used in this study were Personal Information Form, Cyber-aggression Questionnaire for Adolescent, Child Parental Acceptance-Rejection Questionnaire: Father Short Form, Cyber-victimization Questionnaire for Adolescents, and Child Parental Acceptance-Rejection Questionnaire: Mother Short Form. Mean, Standard deviation, t test, correlation and regression analyses were performed to analyze data. The results of this study revealed that there is no gender difference in all the major variables except maternal acceptance-rejection. Pearson product moment correlations demonstrated significant associations among the variables indicating that the higher the parental rejection the higher was both the cyber aggression and the cyber victimization. Mediation regression analyses revealed that parental (both maternal and paternal) rejection had a non-significant direct effect on cyber victimization. Analyses further exhibited significant, indirect effect of maternal rejection through cyber aggression on cyber victimization. Multiple regression analysis showed that maternal and paternal rejection jointly explained about 5% variance in cyber aggression and 7% in cyber victimization among high school children.

Keywords: cyber victimization, perceived parental acceptance-rejection, cyber aggression

The term cyber-aggression is characteristically used to refer to actions that are intentionally hurtful, offensive, or harmful to any individual or institutions using electronic communication devices (Corcoran, McGuckin, & Prentice, 2015). Variations of online harassment among youth and adults using electronic devices and internet have received increased attention by researchers in recent years (Berson, Berson, & Ferron, 2002; Finn, 2004; Ybarra & Mitchell, 2004). Cyber aggression is one of them, and has been empirically linked to multiple maladaptive emotional, psychological, and behavioral outcomes (Patchin & Hinduja, 2006). Nowadays, adolescents spend huge time on the internet,

which may increase the risk of cyberbullying (CB), defined as an aggressive, intentional act carried out by electronic forms, repeatedly and over time, against a victim who cannot defend him/herself (Hinduja & Patchin, 2008). However, the present study uses the terminology of cyber aggression, instead of cyberbullying. Cyber aggression incorporates a variety of intentionally harmful behaviors like spreading rumors, sending offensive messages, hacking someone's online accounts, and impersonating someone else to get others to dislike this person (Grigg, 2010).

With the advancement of technology cyber aggression is increasing day by day. In this, adolescents are being victimized mostly

because of unawareness about its impact. Scholars in recent years have studied the problem and one of the studies found that approximately 15-35% of students have been victims of cyber aggression while about 10-20% of students admit to offend others using cyber space (Williams & Guerra, 2007).

The incident of cyber aggression in Bangladesh has become a matter that must be taken care of. Grameenphone, a leading telecom operator in Bangladesh conducted a study in June-July 2014 with a sample of 1,510 high school students and found that about 70% of the high school students using internet facility in Bangladesh feel helpless in face of cyber-crimes. More than 30% of these users have either been bullied on the internet or received hate mails. The Telenor group, in a new region-wide survey has found that 49% of the school students in Bangladesh have been victims of cyber bullying, revealing that young people are increasingly becoming vulnerable to such harassment.

Cyber victimization among adolescents is a matter that warrants attention due to its prevalence and effects. Preventing cyber victimization among adolescents is of paramount importance. Available research suggests that cyber aggression and cyberbullying often are triggered by victimization, either experienced face-to-face or in the cyber context (e.g., Hinduja & Patchin 2009; Sanders 2009). Patchin and Hinduja (2011) argue that victimization as a source of strain produces feelings of anger and frustration, making victimized adolescents more likely to behave in an aggressive way.

Cyber aggression and victimization in particular have become a matter of concern in schools and communities due to the emotional, psychological, and even physical harm to which victims can be subjected. It is essential to identify its main predictors, including risk and protection factors. Family is the place where they are brought up and so its impact on child is of vital importance. Some authors believe that family has the biggest and direct impact on involvement of children in violence (Hong and Espelage, 2012). According to the research carried out by Hong et al. (2018), parental neglect was related to indirect cyber victimization. Lereya, Samara &

Wolke (2013) conclude that positive parenting, warm and friendly relationship between parents and children is an important protective factor against peer victimization. Similarly, the findings of Mobin et al. (2017) suggested that children who had a poor relationship with their parents were more likely to be a cyber victim. Rejection from parents may lead the child to get engaged in violent behaviors like cyber-crime.

It is obvious that a relationship between parental rejection and cyber victimization exists. A relationship between cyber aggression and cyber victimization is also evident. Several studies have supported that cyber victimization is affected by parental rejection or neglect. However, no study has investigated a model featuring the potential mediational role of cyber aggression regarding the effect of parental rejection on adolescents' cyber victimization. Therefore, present study aimed to test the predictive effect (direct and indirect) of parental rejection on cyber victimization among high school children. Such a model would allow us to gain a better understanding of the pathways through which parental rejection affect adolescents' engagement in various forms of bullying/victimization.

Methods

Sample

Data were collected from 303 high school students (53.5% boys & 46.5% girls) from six schools of Dhaka city in Bangladesh. The participants were selected using purposive convenience sampling technique. The participants were from class eight through class ten and their mean age was 14.89 years (SD =1.11), with a range of 12 through 19 years. Cross-sectional survey research design was used in our study.

Measures

All participants in this research responded to the following self-report questionnaires along with the Personal Information Form (PIF) and they were administered in the following sequence: (1) Personal Information Form (PIF); (2) Cyber-aggression Questionnaire for Adolescents (CYBA); (3) Child Parental Acceptance-Rejection Questionnaire: Father (Child PARQ: Father) Short Form; (4) Cyber-victimization Questionnaire for Adolescents

(CYVIC); (5) Child Parental Acceptance-Rejection Questionnaire: Mother (Child PARQ: Mother) Short Form. Description of these measures are given below:

The Personal Information Form (PIF):

This included demographic, personal, and social information about respondent's gender, age, parental occupation etc.

Cyber-aggression Questionnaire for Adolescents (CYBA): Bangla translated version (Uddin & Rahman, 2018) of this test (Álvarez-garcía, Barreiro-Collazo, núñez, & dobarro, 2016) is a self-report questionnaire. It is composed of 19 items with a Likert-type response format in which the adolescent must indicate how frequently he or she has exercised the aggression described in each statement via mobile phone or the internet in the previous three months (from 1= never to 4 = Always). Example of test items of the scale include, "I have hit a person, recorded the scene and then disseminated it". The sum of the CYBA scale constitutes a measure of overall cyber aggression. The possible scale score ranges from a low of 19 to a high of 76. The midpoint of the scale is 47.5. Score at or above the scale midpoint indicates more cyber aggression. The translated version used in this study has a reliability coefficient, $\alpha = .76$.

Parental Acceptance-Rejection Questionnaire (PARQ): To assess perceptions about current parental (maternal and paternal) acceptance and rejection the Bangla version of Child PARQ/Short Form (Uddin, 2011) was used. The Mother and Father versions of the Parental Acceptance-Rejection Questionnaire (short form) are almost identical – a 24-item, 4-point Likert type self-report measures assessing respondents' perceptions of the warmth/affection, hostility/aggression, indifference/neglect, and undifferentiated rejection they now experience at the hands of their mothers and fathers (Child PARQ). Examples of test items on the both versions of the PARQ Short Form include "My mother/father makes me feel wanted and needed" (perceived warmth or affection); "My mother/father goes out of her/his way to hurt my feelings" (perceived hostility or aggression); "My mother/father ignores me as long as I do to bother

her/him" (perceived indifference or neglect); "My mother/father does not really love me" (perceived undifferentiated rejection). The sum of the four PARQ scales (with the warmth/affection scale reverse-scored to create a measure of coldness/lack of affection) constitutes a robust measure of overall perceived maternal and paternal acceptance-rejection. The possible scale score ranges from a low of 24 to a high of 96. Score at or above the scale midpoint 60 represents more parental rejection than acceptance as perceived by the offspring. The lower is the total PARQ score than the scale midpoint of 60 which is higher, more parental acceptance than rejection as perceived by the offspring. The PARQ has been used in over 400 studies worldwide and is known to have an outstanding reliability and validity for use in cross-cultural research (Khaleque & Rohner, 2002; Rohner, 2005). Alpha coefficient for the Mother PARQ was .805 and for the Father PARQ was .802.

Cyber-victimization Questionnaire for Adolescents (CYVIC): This questionnaire was developed by Álvarez-garcía, Barreiro-Collazo, núñez, & dobarro, 2016 and was translated into Bangla (by Uddin & Rahman, 2018) to assess how frequently the informant has been the victim of attacks via mobile phone or the internet during the previous three months. It consists of 19 statements, with a Likert-type response format (from 1 = never to 4 = Always). The translated version used in this study has a reliability coefficient, $\alpha = .72$. An example of test items of the scale include, "I received calls insulting or mocking me". The sum of the CYVIC scale constitutes a measure of overall cyber victimization. The possible scale score ranges from a low of 19 to a high of 76. The midpoint of the scale is 47.5. A score at or above the scale midpoint indicates more cyber victimization.

Procedure

Consent from participants was taken to collect data at the beginning and each participant was briefed about the general purpose of the study. Participants were given general instructions verbally before going through the items of the scale of how to respond. Then the self-report questionnaires along with a personal information form were administered in classroom

settings. Clarifications were done whenever participants faced any problem understanding the items. It took 20 minutes on an average to complete the task. After the completion, each respondent received a token gift with thanks for their cooperation and participation in the study. The ethical guidelines of the American Psychological Association (APA, 2002) was implemented for conducting research with human participants. Confidentiality and non-maleficence were ensured to participants.

Results

To summarize the findings of the present study, obtained data were analyzed using independent sample t test, Pearson’s product-moment correlation, and regression.

Table 1. Descriptive Statistics and Gender Differences in Major Variables

Variables	Boys (n =162)		Girls (n = 141)		t	P
	Mean	SD	Mean	SD		
Cyber aggression	21.80	3.82	22.07	3.52	-.65	.61
Paternal acceptance-rejection	39.49	8.50	38.62	9.21	.85	.46
Cyber victimization	21.09	3.05	21.41	3.10	-.91	.51
Maternal acceptance-rejection	36.25	7.47	38.01	9.27	-1.83	.033

Result of t test is shown in Table 1. According to the result, there is significant gender difference in perceived maternal rejection. But, there is no gender differences in cyber victimization, cyber aggression, and perceived paternal rejection. According to our findings, girls reported more maternal rejection than boys as perceived by them.

Table 2. Simple correlations among major variables

Variables	1	2	3	4
Cyber victimization	—			
Paternal acceptance-rejection	.23**	—		
Maternal acceptance-rejection	.23**	.62**	—	
Cyber aggression	.48**	.17**	.22**	—

*p < .05; ** p < .01

Simple correlation among major variables were calculated and presented through Table 2. It shows that all the variables are positively correlated with each other. Cyber aggression is moderately and positively (r = .48, p < .01) correlated with cyber victimization. Again, perceived maternal acceptance-rejection is highly and positively correlated with perceived paternal acceptance-rejection (r = .62, p < .01).

To test direct and indirect effects of maternal rejection (covariate paternal rejection) and paternal rejection (covariate maternal rejection), mediation regression analyses were conducted using PROCESS Procedure for SPSS Release 2.16.3 (Hayes, 2018). The results are presented in Tables 3 and 4.

Table 3 indicates that the direct effect of maternal rejection (covariate paternal rejection) on cyber victimization is non-significant (β = .0199, p > .05). The indirect effect of maternal rejection through cyber aggression on cyber victimization is significant (β = .0303, p < .05). Thus, our prediction that maternal rejection indirectly affects cyber victimization through cyber aggression is confirmed.

Table 3. Testing direct effect of maternal rejection (covariate paternal rejection) and indirect effect through cyber aggression on cyber victimization (N = 303)

Maternal Rejection	Effect	SE	t	p	LLCI	ULCI
Total	.0502	.0260	1.9320	.0543	-.0009	.1014
Direct	.0199	.0235	.8494	.3963	-.0262	.0661
Indirect	.0303	.0152	2.4487	.0143	.0039	.0641

Note. Normal theory tests for indirect effect

Effect	se	Z	p
.0303	.0124	2.4487	.0143

Table 4 shows that neither the direct effect nor the indirect effect of paternal rejection (covariate maternal rejection) on cyber victimization is significant (β = .0429, p > .05, β = .0088, p > .05). Thus, it appears that paternal rejection does not directly or indirectly affect cyber victimization.

Table 4. Testing direct effect of paternal rejection (covariate maternal rejection) and indirect effect through cyber aggression on cyber victimization (N = 303)

Maternal Rejection	Effect	SE	t	p	LLCI	ULCI
Total	.0517	.0247	2.0937	.0371	.0031	.1002
Direct	.0429	.0220	1.9468	.0525	-.0005	.0863
Indirect	.0088	.0151	.7729	.4396	-.0184	.0418

Note. Normal theory tests for indirect effect

Effect	se	Z	p
.0088	.0113	.7729	.4396

To show effects in standardized regression coefficient forms, a combined path analysis for results of Table 3 and 4 are simultaneously shown in Figure 1. It shows non-significant effects of maternal rejection ($\beta = .14, p > .05$) and significant effects of paternal rejection ($\beta = .15, p < .05$) on cyber victimization among high school children. The two predictors together explained about 7% variance ($R^2 = .07$) in cyber victimization. When cyber aggression was included in the regression analysis, the effect of maternal and paternal rejection reduced to $R^2 = .05$ and $.12$ ($p > .05$, both). It means that cyber aggression does not mediate the relation between maternal and paternal rejection and cyber victimization among high school children. The three predictors together explained about 26% variance ($R^2 = .26$) in cyber victimization.

Note. $^{***}p < .001, ^{**}p < .01, ^*p < .05$

Figure 1. Path diagram shows the relations between maternal rejection, paternal rejection, cyber aggression, and cyber victimization. Coefficients are standardized regression weights. Coefficients below the path from maternal and paternal rejection to cyber victimization represent the direct effect without the mediator (cyber aggression) in the model, and above the path represent the effect when the mediator is included in the model.

Discussion

The present study investigated whether (a) parental rejection might be the risk factor of cyber victimization, and (b) parental rejection can affect cyber victimization partially through cyber aggression among high school children. Data were collected from 303 high school children administering self-report questionnaires with a personal information form. According to the result, there is a significant gender difference in perceived maternal acceptance-rejection. Girls reported more maternal rejection than boys as perceived by them. But, there was no gender difference in cyber victimization, cyber aggression, and perceived paternal acceptance-rejection.

The findings based on correlation showed that all the four major variables have significant and positive correlation with each other. Cyber aggression is moderately and positively ($r = .48, p < .01$) correlated with cyber victimization. Again, perceived maternal acceptance-rejection is highly and positively correlated with perceived paternal acceptance-rejection ($r = .62, p < .01$). It means that perception of greater rejection from mothers has been found to be associated with perception of greater rejection from fathers also.

Findings from our present study showed that both paternal and maternal acceptance-rejection is positively correlated with both cyber aggression and cyber victimization. The perception of greater parental rejection is associated with greater incidents of cyber aggression and cyber victimization. It may be natural that rejection from parents sometimes have greater impact on child's personality and way of dealing with others. According to previous studies, possible reasons why children are prone to violence and those who experience violence are more likely to feel rejected by parents is the lack of emotional warmth, insufficient and inadequate communication with their parents, and exposure to domestic violence and abuse by parents (Lereya et al., 2013).

Mediation regression analyses revealed that neither maternal nor paternal rejection had a significant direct effect on cyber victimization. Nevertheless, significant indirect effect of maternal rejection has been found through cyber aggression on cyber victimization. We

can conclude that bad relationship of mother and child, emotional coldness and neglecting, incongruous punishment, and inadequate communication generate in child a feeling of rejection from their mother, and as a result the child may show aggressive behavior to peers (Georgiou, 2008; Rigby, 2013) which might lead to subsequent cyber victimization of that child. Lack of warmth, or perception of parental rejection, increases risk that children will develop behavioral problems, particularly externalized, and these factors may be predictors for involvement of children in violent behavior (Rohner, Khaleque & Cournoyer, 2012) like cyber aggression as well as being victimized by peers. Multiple regression analysis showed that maternal and paternal rejection jointly explained only a small amount of variance in cyber aggression ($R^2 = .05, p > .05$) and cyber victimization ($R^2 = .07, p > .05$). There might be some other important variables that should have been considered while investigating the relationship between cyber aggression, cyber victimization, and parental acceptance-rejection.

Conclusion

In all, these findings suggest that parental rejection is positively correlated with both cyber aggression and cyber victimization. Furthermore, we found that there is significant indirect effect of maternal rejection through cyber aggression on cyber victimization. These results of this study may be useful for identifying individuals at risk for engaging in cyber aggression.

Even though our study contributes to the growing literature on adolescents' reason behind getting victimized in cyber space, we acknowledge that other factors may influence aggressive behaviors in the cyberspace. Therefore, we call for follow-up research aiming to disentangle other factors that might play role in the relationships observed in the present study.

References

- Alvarez-Garcia, D., Barreiro-Collazo, A., & Nunez, J. C. (2017). Cyber-aggression among adolescents: Prevalence and gender differences. *Comunicar*, 50, 89–97. <https://doi.org/10.3916/C50-2017-08>
- Alvarez-Garcia, D., Barreiro-Collazo, A., Nunez, J. C., & Dobarro, A. (2016). Validity and reliability of the Cyber-aggression Questionnaire for Adolescents (CYBA). *The European Journal of Psychology Applied to Legal Context*, 8, 69–77. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ejpal.2016.02.003>
- Bauman, S., Toomey, R. B., & Walker, J. L. (2013). Associations among bullying, cyberbullying, and suicide in high school students. *Journal of Adolescence*, 36(2), 341–350. doi: 10.1016/j.adolescence.2012.12.001.
- Berson, I. R., Berson, M. J., & Ferron, J. M. (2002). Emerging risks of violence in the digital age: Lessons for educators from an online study of adolescent girls in the United States. *Journal of School Violence*, 1(2), 51–71.
- Corcoran, L., Mc Guckin, C., & Prentice, G. (2015). Cyberbullying or cyber aggression? A review of existing definitions of cyber-based peer-to-peer aggression. *Societies*, 5, 245–255. <https://doi.org/10.3390/soc5020245>
- Finn, J. (2004). A survey of online harassment at a university campus. *Journal of Interpersonal Violence*, 19(4), 468–483.
- Forty nine percent Bangladeshi school pupils face cyberbullying. (2016, February 09). *The Daily Star*. Retrieved from <https://www.thedailystar.net/bytes/%E2%80%989849-bangladeshi-school-pupils-face-cyberbullying%E2%80%99-287209>
- Georgiou, S. N. (2008). Bullying and victimization at school: The role of mothers. *British Journal of Educational Psychology*, 78(1), 109–125.
- Grigg, D. W. (2010). Cyber-aggression: Definition and concept of cyberbullying. *Australian Journal of Guidance & Counseling*, 20(2), 143–156. doi:10.1375/ajgc.20.2.143
- Hinduja, S., & Patchin, J. W. (2008). Cyberbullying: An exploratory analysis of factors related to offending and victimization. *Deviant Behavior*, 29(2), 1–29.
- Hinduja, S., & Patchin, J. W. (2009). *Bullying beyond the schoolyard: Preventing and responding to cyberbullying*. Thousand Oaks, CA: Sage Publications (Corwin Press).
- Hinduja, S., & Patchin, J. W. (2011). Cyberbullying: A review of the legal issues facing educators. *Preventing School Failure: Alternative Education for Children and Youth*, 55, 71–78.
- Hong, J. S., & Espelage, D. L. (2012). A review of research on bullying and peer victimization in school: An ecological system analysis. *Aggression and violent behavior*, 17(4), 311–322.
- Hong, J. S., Dong H. K., Robert T., Jun H. K., Julie T. M., 2018. Correlates of direct and indirect forms

- of cyberbullying victimization involving South Korean adolescents: An ecological perspective. *Computers in Human Behavior*, 87, 327–36.
- Rigby, K. (2013). Bullying in schools and its relation to parenting and family life. *Family matters*, 92, 61–67.
- Rohner, R. P., Khaleque, A., & Cournoyer, D. E. (2012). Introduction to parental acceptance-rejection theory, methods, evidence, and implications. Retrieved from <http://csiar.uconn.edu/wp-content/uploads/sites/494/2014/02/INTRODUCTION-TO-PARENTAL-ACCEPTANCE-3-27-12.pdf>. (20.4.2017.)
- Khaleque, A. and Rohner, R. P. (2002). Reliability of measures assessing the relation between perceived parental acceptance-rejection and psychological adjustment: A meta-analysis of cross-cultural and intracultural studies. *Journal of Cross-Cultural Psychology*, 33, 86–98.
- Lereya, S., Samara, M., & Wolke, D. (2013) Parenting behavior and the risk of becoming a victim and a bully/victim: a meta-analysis study. *Child Abuse & Neglect*, 37(12), 1091–1108.
- Li, Q. (2006). Cyberbullying in schools: A research of gender differences. *School Psychology International*, 27(2), 157–170. doi: 10.1177/014303430606547.
- Mobin, A., Cindy X. F., Cory N., 2017. Cyber victimization among preadolescents in a community-based sample in Canada: Prevalence and predictors. *Canadian Journal of Public Health*, 108, 475–81.
- Patchin, J. W., & Hinduja, S. (2006). Bullies move beyond the schoolyard: A preliminary look at cyberbullying. *Youth Violence and Juvenile Justice*, 4(2), 148–169.
- Raskauskas, J., & Stoltz, A. D. (2007). Involvement in traditional and electronic bullying among adolescents. *Developmental Psychology*, 43(3), 564–575. doi: 10.1037/0012-1649.43.3.564.
- Rohner, R. P. (2005). Parental Acceptance-Rejection Questionnaire (PARQ): Test manual. *Handbook for the Study of Parental Acceptance and Rejection* 4, 43–106.
- Sanders, J. (2009). Cyberbullies: Their motives, characteristics, and types of bullying. Presentation at the XIV. European Conference of Developmental Psychology, Vilnius, Lithuania.
- Teenagers feel helpless to cyber-crime: Study. (2015, November 28). *The Daily Star*. Retrieved from <https://www.thedailystar.net/country/teenagers-feel-helpless-cyber-crime-study-179350>
- Uddin, M. K. (2011). Parental Warmth and Academic Achievement of Adolescent Children. *Journal of Behavioural Sciences*, 21(1), 1–12.
- Uddin, M. K., & Rahman, J., 2018. Bangla translation of Cyber-aggression Questionnaire for Adolescents (CYBA). Dhaka, Bangladesh: Department of Psychology, University of Dhaka.
- Uddin, M. K., & Rahman, J., 2018. Bangla translation of Cyber-victimization Questionnaire for Adolescents (CYVIC). Dhaka, Bangladesh: Department of Psychology, University of Dhaka.
- Vandebosch, H., & Van, K. C. (2009). Cyberbullying among youngsters: Profiles of bullies and victims. *New Media & Society*, 11, 1349–1371.
- Wang, J., Iannotti, R. J., & Luk, J. W. (2012). Patterns of adolescent bullying behaviors: Physical, verbal, exclusion, rumor, and cyber. *Journal of School Psychology*, 50(4), 521–534. doi: 10.1016/j.jsp.2012.03.004.
- Williams, K. R., & Guerra, N. G. (2007). Prevalence and predictors of internet bullying. *Journal of Adolescent Health*, 41, 14–21.
- Wright, M. F., & Li, Y. (2013). The association between cyber victimization and subsequent cyber aggression: The moderating effect of peer rejection. *Journal of Youth and Adolescence*, 42(5), 662–674. doi: 10.1007/s10964-012-9903-3.

Acknowledgements: This research was supported by Grant in Aid of the University Grants Commission of Bangladesh awarded to the second author.

Jakia Rahman, Lecturer, Department of Psychology, University of Dhaka, Dhaka 1000, Bangladesh. For Correspondence E-mail: jakiavabna@gmail.com

Muhammad Kamal Uddin, Professor, Department of Psychology, University of Dhaka, Dhaka 1000, Bangladesh.

Sardar Mohammad Abu Bakar Siddique, MS student in School Psychology, Department of Psychology, University of Dhaka, Dhaka 1000, Bangladesh.

Protyasha Bhattacharyya, Undergraduate student, Department of Psychology, University of Dhaka, Dhaka 1000, Bangladesh.